

A Study of the evolution and problems of Assamese dictionaries in electronic media---a discussion

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Abstract

With the development of applied linguistics, science and technology gradually became involved in language practice. Different types of science and technology is used in the Assamese language since the 21st century. The practice of Assamese language dictionary through electronic media started from the first decade of the 21st century. There are three types of dictionaries published in electronic media:

A) e-book dictionary

B) Software Dictionary

And c) online dictionary

With the advancement of technology, the addition of dictionaries to the Internet in Assamese is a significant step.

Science and technology are as convenient as they are problematic. It is essential to identify the problems encountered in the use of electronic dictionaries and find solutions. The paper is designed to discuss the evolution and problems of Assamese dictionaries in electronic media.

Key- word: E-book dictionary, software dictionary, online dictionary, problem.

Introduction to the subject:

From the beginning of the twentieth century, theoretical discussions of language began to be discussed with scientific thought. Applied linguistics becomes one of the branches of science. Science and technology gradually began to be applied to languages. The application of technology to the Assamese language in electronic media started from the first decade of the 21st century. The application of technology in the Assamese language is seen in the creation of Unicode, the development of e-magazines, e-dictionaries, etc. Science brings various problems along with contributions. The discussion paper is prepared with the purpose to discuss about the evolution of Assamese dictionaries in electronic media and the problems.

Review of Literature:

In order to discuss the topic “A Study of the Evolution and Problems of Assamese Dictionaries in Electronic Media- A Discussion”, there have been several books in Assamese language discussing Assamese dictionaries in electronic media, specially in ‘*Obhidhanatto*’ by Arpana Konwar discusses about the electronic dictionary through the essay ‘*Axomiya Obhidhan: Goti-Prokriti*’. The article ‘*XOBDO Org*’ by Bikram Majinda Barua published in August this year in the magazine *Goriyoxi* analytically describes the birth, development, conflict and the first word dictionary published in many electronic media.

1.0 Evolution of Assamese Dictionaries in Electronic Media :

Advances in technology have not only inspired systematic studies from a scientific perspective in the fields of science, but have also opened the way for thought in the field of literature. Computers or calculating devices are widely used nowadays. The use of computers for reading and writing, accounting, resource storage, etc. is visible nowadays. As a result of the advancement in science, dictionaries have been produced in digital media. There are two types of computer websites, open source and close source. Open software are free for everyone. Everyone can view the data, and people can connect the data within certain rules. Although dictionary development started with Close software, gradually Open software was used.

The development of a dictionary of the Assamese language began in the late 20th century and early 21st century, and progressed towards completion. Arpana Konwar in her book '*Obhodhanotto*' mentions about the publication of three types of electronic dictionaries in the first decade of the 21st century in the following way--

A) E-Dictionary

B) Software Dictionary

C) Online Dictionary

1.01 E-Book Dictionary:

The first e-book dictionary published in Assamese language was '*Pacchim Asomiya Shabdokosh*' edited by Phanindra Narayan Dutta Baruah. The dictionary was published in 2002 by the Central Institute of Indian Languages [CIL], Mysore. The dictionary includes the languages spoken in the western part of Assam. The dictionary includes meanings in Assamese and English along with practical instructions and examples. The dictionary can be accessed on the Internet by logging on to www.anukriti.net.

1.02 Software Dictionary:

The Assamese Software Dictionary was published in the first decade of the 21st century. In 2010, the first software dictionary in the Assamese language, '*Assamese Software Dictionary*', was published. The dictionary appears to give the meaning of the entries in Assamese. The dictionary also contains grammatical instructions. Looking at the general features of the dictionary, following can be seen----

- 1) literary and cultural concepts are equally provided.
- 2) It allows to download images along with words.
- 3) Proverbs, pictures, computer encyclopedia are provided.
- 4) There is a dependence on the language simplification stage.
- Pt) The list of correct and incorrect forms of the usually used incorrect words are given.
- 6) Symbols of joint letters is arranged in Onscreen keyboard with vowels and consonants.

Anil Baroua has published several dictionaries in 2019 through the ‘*Sarathi*’ Assamese Dictionary [Link] app. This app not only stores dictionaries but also Assamese synonyms, words, phrases, scientific names, terminologies, proverbs, idioms, etc. [Niyomiya Batori, January 13,2020].

The second Assamese software dictionary is ‘*Sahaj Sandhan Asomiya Obhidhan*’ edited by Durlabh Gogoi in 2012. The main feature of the dictionary which consists of 65,285 words is that it judge on the basis of its uniqueness rather than on the basis of Sanskrit language. Almost all the features of ‘Assamese Software Dictionary’ can be visible in ‘*Sahaj Sandhan Asomiya Obhidhan*’.

1.03 Online Dictionary:

In March 2006, ‘*Xobdo*’ became the first Assamese online dictionary available on the Internet. 1,500 members, including Bikram M. Barua, adds words to *Xobdo* and 56 editors edit the words. Since 2007, open source technology has been used. The dictionary includes entries in 27 languages including Assamese language and its meanings in English, *Dimasa*, *Karbi*, *Bodo*, *Miching*, *Khasi*, *Deuri*, *Rabha*, *Tiwa*, Hindi, Nepali etc. It would not be wrong to say that ‘*Xobdo*’ is a multilingual dictionary. You can view the words by logging in to www.xobdo.org.

2.00 Problems of Dictionary Production in Electronic Media

The addition of dictionary in electronic media is very good news for Assamese language and literature. Through language technology, computer programs or electronic devices have created dictionaries to preserve language and words. There are various problems in the development of dictionaries. Knowledge of machine learning, Information Technology is essential to develop a dictionary in electronic media. A student of literature has to acquire knowledge of technology. The initial action of formulation of a dictionary begins only after acquiring scientific knowledge. On the other hand, a linguist is needed simultaneously along with technology expertise. Proficiency in the languages used is essential for the development of a multilingual dictionary in electronic media. Since

literature and technology are two different disciplines, therefore problems in technical knowledge and skills can be seen first.

Some grammatical errors are observed. That's normal, too. In the first step, it is never possible for us to get the most accurate version. Gradually, experts will solve such grammatical problems.

There are many problems in the development of electronic dictionaries in Assamese language due to the lack of people with technological knowledge and skills and lack of awareness of the longevity of the language in the mass media.

Conclusion:

The development of the Assamese language in electronic media began in the early 21st century. Nowadays, the field of Assamese language in electronic media has improved with the advancement of science and technology. We can reach the following conclusions through the discussion paper:

- a) The first E-book dictionary published in Assamese is '*Pacchim Asomiya Obhidhan*' by Fanindra Narayan Dutta Baruah published in 2002.
- b) The first electronic dictionary in Assamese is '*Xobdo*'.
- c) Thousands of words can be seen added to the Assamese online dictionary.
- d) The problem of compiling Assamese dictionaries in electronic media will be solved only through the improvement of language technology and the intervention of skilled linguists.

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